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Agricultural Occupation Inheritance of Farmer in Nong Sam Wang, Nong Suea District, Pathum Thani Province

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Abstract

The present study aims to study the agricultural community in Nong Sam Wang, Nong Suea District, Pathum Thani, Thailand province by interviewing 88 farmers whose main occupation were farmers, cultivating a variety of plants such as, palm, potato, grass sheets, flowers, fruits etc. along with rearing fishes in ponds. Most of the farmers completed only primary educational level. However, most of them cultivated on their own land and land rental from the Treasury Department. Most of the family members contribute their labor collectively in the family agricultural works. Only a few families hired labor from outside. Older farmers usually work in their farm with their offspring because they do not attend school or educated only till the primary level. In case, if their inheritors do not like farming, they usually lease the land to other farmers. Moreover, middle-aged farmers inherited occupation as farmers from their parent.

Keywords: *Inheritance career, agriculture, farmer in Nong Sam Wang*

Background and Rationale

Agriculture sector has been the major income contributors of Thailand's economy since the remote past. The main occupation of major population in Thailand is agricultural cultivation. So, agricultural sector has an important role in Thailand's economic growth and development. However, there are remarkable differences of agricultural incomes as compared to the past. This may be deterioration of natural resources in process along with rapid changes in globalization, economic integration of bilateral and multilateral agreement that have impacted on Thailand agricultural sector and farmers. In this connection, Thailand must adapt to such circumstances. Formulation of agricultural development plan was, therefore, outlined by Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives as guidance procedure of agricultural sector. The scheme emphasizes on the policy of farmer-centered development based on 'Sufficiency Economy Philosophy' as initiated by His Majesty Late King Bhumibol Adulyadej. Specifically, small farmers are enhanced according to the new agricultural theory; while smart farmers are provided with networking and collaboration of farmer's community enterprise or cooperatives. The operation concerns production from knowledge body and innovation with integration of basic technology and then developed as driving forces of local wisdom for inclusive growth.

Agriculture in the present decade usually confronts difficulties on domestic and global agricultural markets. The obstacles include the produces with pesticide cost, high wages together with severe weather, topography. Also, economic conditions that the produce prices are exploited by middlemen. Farmers' incomes do not cover their expenses making in search of loan for farm facilities. They are heavily in debts resulting in difficulties and abject poverty from the past to perpetual present. By these reasons, the youth

inheritors succeed occupation of farmer are not proud to their ancestors at all. In farmers' perspective, the more doing farming occupation, the more they are plunged into poverty and miserable drudge. Therefore, occupational inheritance in farming is not interested in empty areas for agriculture. The youths in the present decade have the view that agricultural occupation can provide them insufficient income, so younger generation people turn to occupation industrial system in industrial zone or working as staffs of private companies in large cities. Public sector has not yet supported occupational inheritance in agriculture which has been the primitive occupation over the past. That why labor scarcity in agriculture sector is currently remarkable.

As mentioned above, local people must pay attention to their quality of life. It is therefore, important to strengthening occupation in agriculture from youth level as youth is the key power of local community in positive drive growth. They will challenge the vital change of local survival with social immunity according to sufficiency economy-based in the future. The corresponding enhancement of occupation in agriculture is carried on by local government officers i.e., provincial agriculture, district agriculture or Sub-district Administration Organization (SAO). The scheme aims to elevate local people's quality of life towards human security and sustainability in development. The important mission is to develop rural people doing agriculture prosper in increasing income, being able to feed themselves and families. That results in sustainable livelihood and good quality of life. The rural youth, youngsters, new generation, the aged, physically challenging people and mentally retarded are important to provide support by bringing over- all growth in rural agriculture sector and the country in the future. In case enhancement and building positive consciousness towards agriculture as an occupation by community leaders, local wisdoms are eligible to navigate creating youth's attitude to cherish their rural communities. They should be supported to empower and to unite so as to manage local wisdom to inherit local wisdom experiences. Networking between the wisdom and the youth in agriculture development is indeed necessary. The interesting programs include the following. Successor of agriculture local wisdom, Dek Hug Thin Project. These would draw the new generation and industrial sector labors to return to agriculture as occupation more in the future. Furthermore, extension of network to the neighboring areas accentuates attention of the youth in occupation in agriculture more in the forthcoming future.

Local administration organization is responsible to enhance and empower people's quality of life. Although, enhancement of agriculture for the youth is not direct responsibility, basic thinking and attitudes in respect of agriculture as occupation are developed to empower the youth interested more in agriculture as occupation. Moreover, such contribution would preserve properly knowledge access of development on agriculture as occupation. For example, culture, inheritance of ancestor's wisdom. The operation will include learning and implementation following Sufficiency Economy Philosophy that will provide strong and self-reliance community. The other way is to nurture creative consciousness for new generation in agriculture.

With this reason, requirement of the youth in agricultural occupation inheritance of ancestor are interested the researcher. Data will be applied for planning and enhancement for the new generations who need to stay and develop their local communities and are loyal to their home living, decrease labor migration, reduce dense industrial cities, create job income opportunities to oneself and communities in the future.

Objectives

To study characteristics in agriculture and agricultural occupation inheritance of people in Nong Sam Wang Sub-district, Nong Suea District, Pathum Province.

Scope of Study

1. The study context in community-based research of Nong Sam Wang Sub-district, Nong Suea District, Pathum Thani Province will include the following aspects:

1.1 Physical conditions and administrative demarcation

1.2 Topography

2.Characteristics of agriculture in Nong Sam Wang Sub-district, Nong Suea District, Pathum Thani Province will explore the following items:

2.1 Numbers and names of villages

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2.2 General information of farmers and agricultural land tenure

2.3 Agricultural activities of households from the start till the present.

Expected Benefits

The research acquires data related to agriculture of households in Nong Sam Wang Sub-district, Nong Suea District, Pathum Thani Province. Collected data are applied for marketing planning in accordance with plants and livestock in the study area. The strategies include creative motivation for the youth, people tended to move for working urban and industrial labor sector who are interested in inherit their ancestor in agricultural occupation.

Outcome

1. Community context Nong Suea District, Pathum Thani Province

- Nong Suea District is of 412.73 km.sq. or 257,000 rai. Office of Nong Suea District is located at 9th km. on the road along Khlong Sib East 50 km away from Pathum Thani Province with its border as given below:

- North is adjacent to Wang Noi Ditrect, Phranakhon Siayudhaya Province; Nong Khae and Vihan Daeng District, Saraburi Provice

- South is adjacent to-Thanyaburi District, Pathum Thani Province

- East is adjacent to Ongkarak District and Ban Na District Nakhon Nayok Province

- West is adjacent to Khlong Luang District Pathumthani Province

Following Local Administrative Act B.E. 2457, Nong Suea District is divided into 7 sub-district, 69 villages as presented in the below figure.

Figure I: Several Sub-district in Nong Suea district

General conditions of Nong Suea District are flat plain suitable for doing paddy, gardening, farming. There are 8 delivery canals and drainage canals connected between Rangsit Prayoosak and Rapipat Canal from the 7th drainage canal to 14th drainage canal. Canal width distance is of 2.4 km. None of mountain or high hill in Nong Suea District is observed. Any river flows through Nong Suea.

Nong Suea’s population are totally of 42,872: male 20,365 and female 22,507. It has a population density of 104 person per square kilometer as shown following.

Table I: Population of Nong Suea District, Pathum Thani Province by Sub-district.

No.	Sub-district	Male(no.)	Female (no.)	Total (No.)
1.	Bueng Ba	3,642	3,081	6,728

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2.	Bueng Bon	3,491	3,731	7,222
3.	Bueng Ka Sam	4,164	3,474	7,638
4.	Bueng Cham Or	2,260	4,472	6,732
5.	Sala Khru	2,241	2,729	4,970
6.	Nopparat	2,254	2,437	4,691
7.	Nong SomWang	2,313	2,583	4,896
Total	-	20,365	22,507	42,872

2. Characteristics of Agriculture and Agricultural Occupation Inheritance of people in Khlong 13

Interview was conducted in Nong Sam Wang District which is divided into 13 villages: Moo 1 Ban Nong Dok Pathum; Moo 2 Ban Nong Sam Wang; Moo 6 Ban Nong Sam Ngam; Moo 7 Ban Nong Bua Luang; 1313Moo 8 Ban Nong Sa Nak; Moo 9 Ban Nong Tha Lae; Moo 10 Ban Nong Bung Yai; Moo 11 Ban Nong Na Sanan; Moo 12 Ban Nong Na Sa-nguan and Moo 13 Ban Nong Dok Sa-noe.

2.1 Characteristics of agricultural activities of farm household

Farmers in Nong Sam Wang Sub-district completed only primary education level and were trained in planting, fertilizer and chemical utilization in agriculture; making compost, micro-organism fertilizer; soil analysis, charcoal-burning, Sufficiency Economy Philosophy. Most Agricultural labor are household labor. Some are hired from outside. Agricultural lands are both their own land and rent from Treasury Department. Farmers in Nong Sam Wang did orange orchard and all were disrupted by epidemic disease, citrus canker. The farmers cultivate and rear the following:

1. Paddy
2. Vegetables as lemon grass, cow pea, gourd, bitter gourd, lemon, calabash, mushroom, chili, pea eggplant, cucumber, morning glory
3. Fruit orchard consisting of banana, mango, guava, papaya, orange, marian plum (Ma Prang), sweet marian plum (Ma Yong Chit)
4. Palm and yam
5. Fish rearing both in pond and floating cages consisting of cat fish, climbing perch etc.

Table II: Numbers of years doing agriculture by household agricultural activities

Household agricultural activities	Numbers of years doing Agriculture		
	1-20 yrs	21-40 yrs	41-60 yrs
Paddy field	8 (29.63)	4 (14.81)	15 (55.56)
Fruit orchard	21(65.63)	3 (9.38)	8 (25.00)
Flowers, ornamental plants/grass sheet/yam	4 (100.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
Inland fishery	3 (50.00)	1 (16.67)	2 (33.33)
Vegetation	10 (66.67)	2 (13.33)	3 (20.00)
Palm tree	0 (.00)	1 (50.00)	1 (50.00)
Total	46 (53.49)	11 (12.79)	29 (33.72)

Based on the above table, most of farmers who do paddy field started their occupation from 41-60 years. While other occupation, except for planting palm trees, started mentioned occupation not greater than 20 years.

Table III: Size of agricultural land by household activities

Household agricultural activities	Land size		
	not greater than 20 rai	21 – 80 rai	100 – 830 rai
Paddy field	9 (33.33)	17 (62.96)	1(3.70)
Fruit orchard	24 (75.00)	6 (18.75)	2(6.25)
Flower/ ornamental plants/yam/ Grass sheet	4 (100.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
Inland fisher/palm tree	4 (50.00)	4 (50.00)	0 (0.00)
Vegetation	13 (86.67)	1 (6.67)	1 (6.67)
Total	54 (62.79)	28 (32.56)	4 (4.65)

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From the table, most of farmers have agricultural land 21-80 rai. While those do fruit orchard and vegetation have subsistence land not greater than 20 rai. Also, those plant flowers, ornamental plants, yam grass sheet, all had subsistence land not greater than 20 rai.

Table IV: Land tenure for agriculture by household agricultural activities

Household agricultural activities	Agricultural land tenure	
	Owned	Hire
Paddy Field	10 (37.04)	17 (62.96)
Fruit orchard	10 (31.25)	22 (68.75)
Flowers/ornamental plants/yam	2 (100.00)	0 (0.00)
Inland fishery	2 (33.33)	4 (66.67)
Vegetation	6 (40.00)	9 (60.00)
Palm trees/grass sheet	0 (0.00)	3 (100.00)
Total	30 (34.88)	56 (65.12)

Based on the table, the findings are that the farmers who do paddy field, fruit orchard, inland fishery, vegetation, almost rent farmland for agriculture. While those who plant flowers, ornamental plants/yam, observed only one household each, all have their own land for subsistence agriculture. While those who plant palm trees/grass sheet, all rent farmland for agriculture.

2.2 Household Agricultural Inheritance

Farmers in Nong Sam Wang Sub-district are rather elderly who have assisted their parents in agriculture since they were young till the present. As their children and descendants do not go to school or merely educate at primary education level. Agricultural activities are carried on by household labor. Furthermore, some families whose their members do other occupation such as civil servant, trader, private business, private company staff. Certainly, at the end of working period, they are interested in occupation inheritance in agriculture from their parents. The reason is that their children do another jobs for a while, until they are bore some and would like to support their parents in agriculture. However, they must maintain their present job. In case, the descendants do not tend to remain within families, the farmers must offer the other for agricultural holding (rental land). Also, the findings were that middle aged-farmers will remain farm inheritance from their parents. Their descendants, who are school-children, will assist doing agriculture when they are available. Some households whose their children remain so young, therefore, they could not provide the answer whether will remain agriculture within families.

Table V: Agricultural Occupation Inheritance by household activities

Household activities	Agriculture inheritance			
	Doing with descendant within families	Inheritance from parents, descendant do 1 jobs and assume to support household when parents get older	Inheritance from parents but not sure of descendant's inheritance as they are school-children/no children	Inheritance from parents and descendants do not remain within families, may lease the land to other farmers
Paddy field	16 (59.26)	4 (14.81)	2 (7.41)	5 (18.52)
Fruit orchard	15 (46.88)	8 (25.00)	3 (9.38)	6 (18.75)
Flowers/ornamental plants/yam	2 (100.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
Inland fishery	4 (66.67)	0 (0.00)	1 (16.67)	1 (16.67)
Vegetation	5 (33.33)	5 (33.33)	2 (13.33)	3 (20.00)
Palm trees	0 (0.00)	2 (100.00)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)
Grass sheet	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (50.00)	1 (50.00)
Total	42 (48.84)	19 (22.09)	9 (10.47)	16 (18.60)

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From the tables, the farmers doing paddy field, planting fruit orchard and inland fishery, most will tend agriculture occupation inheritance with descendants within families. While those also plant vegetation doing with the same manner and succeed from their parents whose children and descendants working another jobs, however, assumed to turn to support the families when getting older. Those plant ornamental plants/yam are observed each and do agricultural inheritance occupation remaining with descendant within families.

Research Opinion

Farmers in Nong Sam Wang Sub-district do agriculture with several kinds such as doing paddy field, planting fruit orchard, vegetation, palm trees, yam, inland fishery, grass sheet, flowers, ornamental plants. The same characteristic is that farmers with rather old age who support their families since they were children. Their descendants participate agriculture activities and inherit agriculture occupation in the future. As their descendant do not go to school or finish primary education. Some cases whose their descendants go to work in private companies in Bangkok or separated from families after getting married, they foresee that they would certainly turn back to remain agricultural occupation in the future. While middle aged-farmer will inherit agriculture occupation from their parents. Some whose their descendants are still infant or school-children, so they could not provide the answer whether they will inherit agricultural occupation.

In consequence, enhancement of farm youth for agricultural occupation should be primarily done form middle aged-farmer's families. The strategy should be in co-operation with local wisdom or elder farmers to transfer agricultural knowledge to local youth. For that they will cherish and pay interest to inherit agricultural occupation from their parents. Furthermore, Sub-district Administration Authority (SAO) should take part in planning for disseminating agriculture information with new technology to the communities. The activities include implementation whether the knowledge transfer could be into practice or not and to draw the youth's attention for farm skill development in the future.

Suggestion for Further Study

The future research should be related to guidance on enhancement of innovative technologies in agriculture. The target should be Kamnan (village chief), village head, Chief of Sub-district Administration, Deputy of Sub-district Administration. Key effective strategies emphasize on simply communication approaching to young famers and being easy to transfer into practice. The challenging includes proper implementation on how much the farmers can transfer knowledge in practice.

References

- i. *Agriculture Heritage in India. (2017). Introductory Agriculture: (Agro 102).* <http://eagri.org/eagri50/AGRO102/lec01.pdf>
- ii. *Alsgaard H. (2012). Rural inheritance: gender disparities in farm transmission. North dakota law review. 88:347.*
- iii. *Asawasathien C. (2014). Guidance of Young Smart Farmer towards Agricultural Leader. An article of Department of Agricultural Extension. available from <http://www.edoae.doe.go.th/articel18022557.pdf>*
- iv. *Australian Farming Families: Succession and Inheritance. (2016). Chapman Eastway. http://chapmaneastway.com.au/sites/default/files/CE_Succession%20Report.pdf*
- v. *Barclay E., Foskey R. and Reeve I. (2007). Farm Succession and Inheritance: Comparing Australian and International Trends. Rural Industries Research and Development Corporation. Kingston, Australia.*
- vi. *Blomquist J. , Nordinb M. and Waldoa S. (2016). In the Footsteps of their Fathers: Exploring Occupational Inheritance in Swedish Agriculture and Fisheries. AgriFood Economics Centre WORKING PAPER. 1:1-27.*
- vii. *Building Thailand with Heart Smart of Agriculture. https://www.moac.go.th/download/article/article_20110803142621.pdf*
- viii. *Chuachomkate S. (2019). Inheritance of Farming Occupation in Tambon Bang Pasee, Bang Lane District, Nakhornpathom Province. Independent Study Labor and Welfare Development Thammasat University.*

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- ix. *Colleran H. (2014). Farming in transition: land and property inheritance in a rural Polish population. Society. Biology & Human Affairs 2014. 78(1&2):7-19.*
- x. *Fadsura V. and Narot P. (2015). The Interest and Need of Youth in Agricultural Occupation: A Case Study of Ban Thaen Subdistrict Administration Organization, Chaiyaphoom Province. Journal of Political Science and Law, Kalasin Rajabhat University Journal. 4(1):Jan-Jun 2015.*
- xi. *Jindal B. (2014). Are Inheritance Rights of Women in Agricultural Land A Mirage ?.International Journal of Law and Legal Jurisprudence Studies. 1(7):1-18.*
- xii. *Kwanmuang K. (2015). Farmland Inheritance, Transaction and Transference: A Case Study in the Southern Region of Thailand. 2015:46-51.*
- xiii. *Maejo Poll. (2011). Thailand's Future Crisis Scarcity of New Generation of Successors in Agricultural Occupation.*
- xiv. *Nilesh A. F. (2015). Shackled to the Soil: The Long-Term Effects of Inherited Land on Labor Mobility and Consumption. available from https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/nileshf/files/anf_jmp.pdf*
- xv. *Phetpuang A. (2014). Inheritance of Durian Occupation Farmer in Nonthaburi Province. Thesis on Master of Arts (Thai Studies). Ramkhamhaeng University.*
- xvi. *Rogers C. and Salamon-U S. (1983). Inheritance and social organization among family farmers. American Ethnologist. 10:529-550.*
- xvii. *Roongrathawatchai P. (2011). Anticipating Thailand Farmer Shortage!. Manager 360 °. October 2011. <http://info.gotomanager.com/news/details.aspx?id=93300>.*
- xviii. *Russell T. (2014). Supporting farm families in making decisions on succession and inheritance: An Irish perspective on policies and support programmes. available from <https://www.brandonusca/rdi/files/2014/03/Irish-Farm-Succession-Presentation.pdf>*
- xix. *Žutinić Đ. And Grgić I. (2010). Family farm inheritance in Slavonia region, Croatia Agric. Econ. – Czech, 56: 522–531.*